

IMPACT OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATORS IN A TRANSFORMATION PROCESS: Nigeria EXPERIENCE

Oaikhena I.E. Marvellous

Department of Public Administration
College of Management and Social Sciences
Samuel Adegboyega University, Ogwa, Edo State.
prince_marv12@yahoo.ca

and

Idehen Roosevelt

Department of International Relations and Strategic Studies
College of Arts and Social Sciences
Igbinedion University, Okada, Nigeria

Abstract

Transformation is the creation and change of a whole new form, function or structure. To transform is to create something new that has never existed before and could not be predicted from the past. The effort put in place by public administrators in the transforming process is a catalyst for growth, national renewal and a lasting source of comparative advantage, which will become very significant and paramount to the state. As a state, Nigeria has failed to meet the basic human needs of its population; it lacks transparent and accountable political institutions and it has not produced sustainable or equitable economic growth. The overall goal of public administrators amongst others' is to guarantee the wellbeing and productivity of the people, by promoting the eradication of negative vices like extreme hunger and poverty. While efforts are geared towards promoting sustainable housing, access to micro-credit, gender equality, transparency and accountability in budget implementation etc. Against this backdrop this paper is set to examine innovations and best practices by Nigerian public administrators in a democratic society towards transformation process, as it recognizes the variety of operational and strategic challenges, which policymakers ought to address, in order to achieve ultimate goal and raise the quality of service delivery to the citizens. The study submits that in spite of daunting challenges such as lack of political and bureaucratic commitments, some progress has been made by the public administrators towards achieving sustainable democratic environment and repositioning administration for higher levels of efficiency and effectiveness in service delivery. Accordingly, recommendations were made to enable administrators fare better in the discharge of their duties to the citizens and to the society in general.

Key words: Transformation, Public Administrators, Bureaucracy, Accountability, Democracy

Background of Study

To transform means to change in form, appearance or structure. Transformation in the context of the management of society, organizations and systems occurs first in individuals. Transformation has become synonymous with change and development in the society. Development is a process that involves the progress of people in the society. Since people live within some form of social framework consisting of social, economic and political structures, development involves changes or transformation of these structures. The human and spatial development components, aimed at transforming Nigeria's six geo-political zones into major economic hubs, capable of supporting the envisaged agenda of the Nigeria state is paramount and can be realized through bureaucratic transformation in a democratic environment. This transformation will guarantee the well-being and productivity of the people, as human development is the ultimate goal of all developmental efforts. The promotion of the well-being of the people to generate human capacity that will drive expected growth is critical to the attainment of key policies for improving the wellbeing and productivity of Nigerians through the efforts of administrators.

Therefore, an efficient administrator is one who gives proper weight to all ends and means that are relevant to his activity. Thus, according to Simon, quoted by Aghayere (2004) he posit that, the fundamental criterion of an administrative decision must be "efficiency", as he categorized efficiency as an operational criterion for decision-making. Decision making depends upon the availability of facts and the necessary data. Data, that should be produced by public administrators, as they are faced with deciding whether a policy is implementable or not.

In addition, for a good policy to be implementable in a democratic environment, the first step is the transformation of the individual(s). This transformation is a continuous process. It comes from understanding the system with profound knowledge. The individual(s) transformed, will perceive new meaning to life, to events, and interactions between people. Once the individual(s) understands the system of profound knowledge, they would apply its principles in every kind of relationship with other people. As Deming (1993) puts it "they would have a basis for judgment of their own decisions and for transformation of the establishment that they belong to".

Transformation is what happens when people see the world through a new lens of knowledge and are able to create an infrastructure, never before envisioned, to the future.

Transformation is motivated by survival, by the realization that everything needs to change or the establishment will die; that a significant breakthrough in mindset is needed in order to pursue new opportunities. Unfortunately, few individuals understand transformation or why there is an imperative for transformation, not merely incremental or transitional change. Hence often, people confuse transformation with any kind of change, technology breakthrough, innovation, process improvement or transition.

However, few changes are truly transformational. The study noted that people all over the world are negotiating rapid social, economic and technological change, in both contexts of growth and decline, while others crave for administrative change, where democracy and good governance will be freely applied in the state. The redefinition of the role of the state or public sector involves the need to overhaul administrative system and rejuvenate the public sector in a developing country like Nigeria. This is because though the dawn has been clouded and goals cannot be easily defined, the vitality of a country's development depends on the rejuvenation of public administrators even in the darkness of insufficient knowledge and experience. There is a vision of transformation in our public administrators, but the specific systems and processes are created through continuous learning and taking new actions, "actions and decisions never before taken".

From the forgoing, the basic functions of administrators is to provide goods and services to citizens based on the realization and representation of public interests and its possession of unique public qualities compared to business management. However, the public sector has not been able to perform its functions effectively because Nigeria is seen as a weak state, learning towards failure. Nigeria meets the criteria for state weakness as established by the Brookings Institution's Index of State Weakness. The lack of accountability and proper representation, indifference towards public needs, ethnicity and religiosity plays a role in politicizing the public sphere. This ineffectiveness coupled with the economic crisis of the late 1970s and 1980s and the apparent lessons from international experience of the success of market friendly economies have combined to produce what some scholars have referred to as the "redistribution of the role of the state or public sector" (Fizbein, 2000).

The public sector need to work towards the eradication of poverty efficiently through the reviewing of the nations approach to the implementation of poverty reduction policies and programmes which, historically, have been a top-down approach, with government developing programmes for the people rather than programmes designed, implemented,

monitored and evaluated by the people themselves. It has been argued and accepted that the state had a legitimate and positive role to promote the welfare of the people. This could be the reason why Saidai referenced Mill (1939) maintained that phrases like ‘self-government’ or ‘power of the people’ do not express the truth. The ‘will of the people’ practically meant the will of the most numerous and the most active part of the people, i.e., the majority. He also writes that “a state which dwafs its men in order that they may be more docile instruments on its hands even for beneficial purposes, will find that with small men no great things can really be accomplished (www.jeywin.com.2009).

Statement of Problem

Transformation is a dynamic process that is correlated with economic growth through the improvement of productivity and provision of goods and services to the people. Thus, Nigeria public administrators, need to face the challenges of transforming the economy to create wealth, reduce poverty, minimize inequalities, strengthen productive capacities, enhance social conditions of its people and achieve sustainable development. Transformation in an economy, promotes social development and inclusive growth by diversifying the sources of growth; creating job opportunities; promoting rural development; and enhancing human capital and productivity through strengthened health and education systems as well as fiscally sustainable social protection systems. This paper is set to find out why successful transformation programmes by Nigeria government, had been undermined by internal factors. Internal factors like poor economic management, poor planning design, poor policy implementation, weak institutional and individual capacities, limited investment in technology to drive the economy; and lack of public accountability. The effectiveness of a state in shaping the transformation agenda hinges on the appropriateness of its vision and the level of its capacity for prudent management of the economy. The paper thereafter submits that, a transformation process that is all inclusive, democratic and participatory enough ensures a broad spectrum of stakeholders vital for sustainability. As a result, the objective of this paper is to among others ascertain:

- If internal factors are responsible for failures in the transformation of a society;
- if public administrators are contributing meaningfully towards sustainable transformation in a democratic society, like Nigeria; and
- to what extent are public administrators promoting economic transformation in Nigeria

Major Internal Factors Inhibiting Transformation in Nigeria

The Nigerian society is presently afflicted with unresolved societal malaise such as militancy (Akinwale, 2010; Umoh, Thompson and Adick, 2012), insecurity (Arpomuvire and Egbadju, 2010; Hazen and Horner, 2007) and poverty (Kumolu, 2012). Compounding these vices is the upsurge of corruption. The interplay of these forces has placed Nigeria in a state of disequilibrium as activities in various social institutions have become rather unethical and synonymous with decadence. In the words of Akindele (1995), just a handful would disagree with the contention that in Nigeria today, nepotism, extortion, bribery, embezzlement, favouritism, fraud etc., have become a way of life and have affected the vital structures and organs of government that make for Nigeria's progressive functioning, thus putting her very existence and planned transformation process in serious jeopardy. These negative vices in Nigeria reflects the collapse of almost all its strategic national institutions - the bureaucracy, the judiciary, the police, the schools system, etc.- what we now have is a paradoxical service: ignorant, unimaginative, over bloated and careerist. In some very important respects, there is strength in that background, and in many other fundamental respects, there is weakness of the sort that can lead to a potential misreading that might end up misdirecting the necessary changes required to transform the Nigerian state for greater efficacy.

Succinctly, Nigeria's development efforts have over the years been characterized by lack of continuity, consistency and commitment to agreed policies, programmes and projects as well as an absence of a long-term perspective. The culminating effect has been growth and development of the Nigerian Economy without a concomitant improvement in the overall welfare of Nigerian citizens.

Public Administrators as Catalyst for Transformation

According to Cheema (2004), public confidence in the political system and subsequently the political legitimacy of the government is increased where the public service delivery system is effective, where the public officials are accessible to local citizens, and where government agencies and departments work together in well coordinated, complementary ways.

Whenever people work together, there is generally a need for the coordination of efforts in order to attain expected results in reasonable time, and with minimum amount of money, discomfort or energy. This could be the reason why Leon (1979:139), posit that

“political parties tend not to generate issues, preferring instead to respond to issues raised by the public or by pressure groups”. Thus the major problem of most developing countries, especially immediately after independence and which persist till date in many of them is the acute dearth of public sector administrators trained in policy formulation. This implies that most often policy goals and expectations are often not considered as they lack clarity, internal inconsistency and incompatibility with other policy agendas. All these affect the chances for successful implementation of policies that would have lead to the desired change by the public administrators under a democratic dispensation.

It is anticipated that public administrators in developing economy like Nigeria, has specialists personnel who will be more involved, more effective, analytical in policy making process, with management education and training, management development and career plans, industrial relations, compensation package problems and such overall corporate decision making process that can programme the manpower plan and complement the corporate plans, thereby leading to the achievement of corporate objectives, hence the reformation programme of government has proved to be more useful.

However in spite of these attributes leading to reforms, some public sectors have remained inefficient and ineffective towards proper transformation. Their continued poor performance has been blamed on a number of factors which are set out as follows:

- a. Reforms were said to be mainly seen in technical and managerial terms rather than in political and institutional terms because public administration are embedded in a complex, interdependent system. This system incorporates not only the bureaucratic apparatus as a whole, but also political institutions and social, economic, and political interests more broadly.
- b. Most of the reforms are said to be nested in politics. For instance, whereas many governments agreed to reduce the number of ministries as part of the retrenchment exercise they have often resorted to the temptations of increasing the number of ministries and perastatals. The introduction of multi-party politics in Nigeria has reinforced the pressure to reward followers as part of coalition building government. The result is that democratic reforms have often worked against the necessary consistency in reforming the public sector.
- c. Reforms have failed to respond to the livelihood concerns of employees (poor working conditions and inadequate salaries for public sector employees have continued due to the need to rescue government expenditure) and requirement that

recruitment be frozen with its attendant admonition to underpaid and poorly motivated workers to assume additional responsibility and to lead efforts at improving efficiency.

- d. Nigerian bureaucrats, suffer from weak organizational culture, as a result emphasis is being put on motivation rather than on public service ethos of commitment, professionalism and promoting public service and interest.
- e. There is low demand for quality service and good performance from citizens, clients, users and civil society organization, which has made operation of public organizations not only unresponsive and unaccountable but also fraught with neo-patrimonial logics.

However, the trends in reforming the public sector in Nigeria showed that they were influenced by politicization, economic liberalization and democratization. They are perceived to have been driven by mainly donors rather than “homegrown”. In each of the trends emphasis was placed on accountability, improved service delivery, good governance and economic development. One significant outcome of the trends is that they show mixed results mainly because public expectations are fundamentally different, while the notions of public service ethos or civil service culture have not changed as envisaged. Perhaps the legacy of the trends in reformation is to constrain the public officials to ensure that public expectations provide motive, and building basic public sector disciplines to provide capability and avoid failures. As Manning (2001) puts it “even though the direct application of the reforms has been limited and has achieved little in African states, they have significantly altered the public management debate both for governments and for development agencies”.

Leadership Failures in Societal Transformation

According to Oaikhena (2011), people are more committed to actions where they are involved in the relevant decision-making and are less competitive and more collaborative when they are working on joint goals. He added that leadership is about the future and the ability to energize others to pursue it. There should be a great consensus among public administrators on what to be done to accelerate growth, reduce poverty, improve governance and assume leadership and accountability for the nation’s development. This could be the reason why Preboye (2005:97) assert that “there is a phenomenon, where the country seems to be getting richer and the citizens are getting poorer”. The failure inherent in the management of affairs by public administrators is as a result of ineffective leadership and

lack of commitment. This lack of commitment has led to the non-provision of visible and focused leadership from the very highest level of administration. As a result allocation of resources and aligning of policies to enable societal growth and transformation has been hampered. As posit by Tzu (2005), solidarity dills especially for mutual understanding and rapport between the leadership and the followers, achieved through both education and training.

Public administrators need to imbibe the spirit of transformational leadership that is central to successful implementation of transformation process and programmes. Transformational leaders are idealized in the sense that they are a moral exemplar of working towards the benefit of the team, organization and/or community. They redesign perceptions, values and change expectations and aspirations of the people in the society. Thus the table hereunder threw more light on the old bureaucratic organization and the new public administration, according Olaopa (2008).

Old Bureaucratic Organization	New Public Administration
Emphasis is place on the need of the organization, thus making it an end in itself	The primary focus is on efficient services delivery to the citizens or the clients of the organization.
Hierarchical with emphasis on control and compliance	Stresses participatory leadership driven by shared values.
Authority and control are centralized	Authority and control are decentralized
Emphasis continuity and stability	Change-oriented; hence emphasis is placed on innovation and continuous improvement.
Programmes are budget driven that is, financed largely by appropriation	Programmes are revenue-driven that is, on cost recovery basis.
Based on the idea that government has monopoly on service delivery	Based on the idea of competition with the private sector on service delivery

The question one may tend to ask is, do Nigeria public administrators, need a revolutionary breed of leaders? Perhaps it was in response to this kind of question that, Marwa and Zairi (2009) proposed a revolutionary breed of leadership that would consistently promote efficiency, honesty, productivity and public offerings while fiercely standing against illegitimate political forces, this they concluded is very critical. Thus, is Nigeria currently

witnessing this style of revolutionary leadership?, *viz-a-viz* the change mantra of President Mohamradu Buhari, who has taken bold steps to effect transformation in the country by ensuring that the various governmental institutions/structures are strengthened to meet desired goals.

Contributing towards a Sustainable Developmental Transformation Process

According to Cameron and Gibson (2001) referencing Young, they expressed the desire to overcome individualism and difference, to produce social wholeness and mutual identification in successful transformation process. Transformation is a “change” in mindset. It is not because the system is evil or undemocratic (Leon, 1979). It is based on learning a system with profound knowledge and taking actions based on leading with knowledge and courage which are essentially based on the promotion of sustained socio-economic development. Development then becomes a process that involves the progress of people in the society. According to Priboye (2005,109) “societies are unequal in their distribution of power, material and social rewards and it is these inequality that generate social divisions and conflict of interest. Since people live within some form of social framework consisting of social, economic and political structures, development involves changes or transformation of these structures. In order to sustain these structures public servants need to perform relatively well in terms of technological advancement, unity, economic needs and equality. Economic needs cannot be realistic, if a society is economically un-equals as gross inequalities make a liberty of the few. This was why Saidai (2006) quoted Laski that “an interest in liberty begins when men ceased to be overwhelmed by the problem of sheer existence”.

Liberty and equality as opposed to each other has been an important current of early liberalism, since positive liberalism developed in the twentieth century. This early development created an atmosphere of communal living which gradually led to the transformation of the society, thereby bringing people of diverse background together to move the society forward, through various contributions. These contributions came from various bodies and organizations. These organizations managed to persist in a context of weak statehood and poor performance, and have the potential to trigger or inspire positive transformations of other public organizations or even the environment or society in the near future. This could be the reason why Heifitz and Linsky (2002) opined that leadership would be a safe undertaking if organizations and communities only face problems for which they already knew the solutions. This invariably calls for effective communication.

Communication is an essential ingredient for (Makinde, 2005) effective implementation of public policy. Through communication, orders to implement policies are expected to be transmitted to the appropriate personnel in a clear manner while such orders must be accurate and consistent. The absence of this inadequate information can lead to misunderstanding on the part of the implementors who may be confused as to what exactly are required of them. In effect, implementation of instructions that are not transmitted, that are distorted in transmission, that are vague, or that are inconsistent may cause serious obstacles to policy implementation (Makinde, 2005). As a result, sustainable development in Nigeria by public administrators should be characterized by five main attributes: (i) high quality livelihood; (ii) peace, stability and unity; (iii) good governance; (iv) a well educated and learning society; and (v) a competitive economy capable of producing sustainable growth and shared benefits.

In these regard, the nation seeks to actively mobilize the people and other resources towards the achievement of shared goals. It instills the courage and determination to rise to challenges at the individual, community and national levels in terms of performance. This performance system which should be installed in the public service aims at having in place predictable, effective and efficient systems for planning, implementation, monitoring, evaluation and reporting in the public service. The overall objectives of these interventions are to: (i) provide quality public services to the public; (ii) improve performance of public service institutions; (iii) improve accountability and responsiveness; (iv) ensure effective and efficient use of public resources; and, (v) provide standards for providing comparisons and benchmarking within the public service institutions in Nigeria as well as other public service institutions across the world for continuous improvement and economic transformation.

Societal Transformation

Societal transformation calls for a community of practice of consultants and leaders informed by such understandings. Many people are engaged as change agents in organizational, governance and societal change. According to Drucker (1994), far smaller and far slower social changes in earlier periods triggered civil wars, rebellions, and violent intellectual and spiritual crises. Today there has been a growing realization of the fact that development is not only defined by the economic and social conditions of a country but equally by its societal achievements, i.e. by the capacities of state and non-state actors to

democratically interact and share the public space within which the common good of each society is to be defined and implemented.

A sustainable use of our natural resources largely depends on the societal capacities of citizens and communities for inter-sectoral and long-term intergenerational responsibility. As a result societies are acknowledging more and more the need to move from vertical structures of command and obedience (such as patriarchy) to the concept of partnership, from ideologically or militarily defined and justified dictatorships to democratic governance essentially based on participatory processes and the capacity to relate to other. Participatory process was described by Oaikhena (2011) as a situation where “members of the group feel more engaged in a process, as creativity makes them likely to care for the end result”. It may then be argued that, given the present poor state of Nigeria’s economy, a fundamental factor in the promotion of rural development is the awareness and initiative of the rural community itself and the extent of its involvement and participation in the development of its area. This argument is predicated on the notion that the resources of the federal government are limited and cannot therefore provide everything for every community. It can be reiterated that people are usually willing to co-operate with one another to satisfy their mutual interests. It is perhaps in recognition of this that the federal government as part of the objective of the 1976 local government reforms included the mobilization of human and material resources through the involvement of members of the public in their local developmental areas. Thus, Ogunnowo and Oderinde (2012), contended that rural transformation is *sine-qua-non* to national development. Therefore for the successful attainment of this development, public administrators should enhance community development through effective participation in rural programmes for effective transformation. The capacity of public administrators to participate in the common public space ultimately defines the societal cohesion and the building of communities, the achievement of the rule of law and of good governance as well as of peace and security of economic, social and environmentally sustainable development.

Framework of Analysis

A theory of transformation means there will be a profound change in structure that creates something new. The system of profound knowledge provides the *method for transformation*. Transformation occurs through a system of continual questioning, challenging, exploration, discovery, evaluation, testing, and creation of an organization’s management theory and application; beginning with the realization or revelation that the

organization's current thinking (i.e., management theory) is incomplete. This was why Gibson and Cameron (2001) argued that "community has entered policy debate via a new language of economic management, as it has also assumed its inherently geographical association with the 'local' and place based concerns".

Succinctly, transformation has no clear destination as the journey has never been traveled before hence the result is uncertain and unpredictable. It embraces new learning and taking actions based on the new discoveries. As a result not everyone will accept transformation. Leaders need to prepare the people for the journey. Leaders need to acknowledge the fears that transforming an organization or society would create fear, as people fear losing their jobs, making mistakes, and speaking up. This has also led to strong resistance to change. Transformation invites criticism, when management of organization, institution or society needs to do things differently. The result according to Adebayo (2008) is that officials tend to take pains to examine every issue from all possible points of view, as they endeavour to establish a uniform body of precedent for application to cases that arise, in order to prevent accusations of partiality or favouritism. Unfortunately, too many leaders are not taking the time to think about what they are doing and the impact of their actions and the "best practices" they are imposing. In their aggression for accountability they create stress, internal competition, sub-optimized systems, and loss. They also begin to lose control of the vision and objective of the organization and do not understand why.

Vision is an ever-evolving picture of the future. At the beginning of the transformation process, that vision can include an exciting sense of the "better way". It can also include a terrifying view of what can happen if things remain unaltered. Once on the transformation path, it is an ever-evolving flood of opportunities. The vision must be collaborative because one person will not be able to articulate everything. The journey will be difficult. Fears are abundant: the fear of change, of loss, of the unknown, of making mistakes, of failure, of "not getting it," etc. On the other hand, as others awaken and join the transformation process, barriers and "silos" will break down, collaboration and synergy will be incredible; the creativity and innovation will be staggering.

Summary/Conclusion

The CHANGE mantra of the administration of President Muhammadu Buhari, is a laudable one as it is geared towards the transformation process of public or private administrators in Nigeria. Nigeria is home to some prominent, intellectual and hard working

individuals, who are willing to embrace transformation at will. But for some few corrupt and lazy individuals who have taken it upon themselves to sabotage and maneuver the course of events. Transformation would therefore, appear to follow that there is a limit to the size of any institution or organization beyond which efficiency begins to decline and concern for the human element disappears and become irrelevant. This notion is not restricted to government alone. It is also true of business organizations and other large institutions.

The study, therefore assumes that there is a greater consensus among Nigerians on what needs to be done to accelerate growth, reduce poverty, improve governance and assume leadership and accountability for even development. With better leadership, economic governance would improve, resulting in fewer conflicts and an improvement in the general economic outlook, business environment and investment outlook. The leadership of the nation should therefore promote meritocracy rather than ethnicity or tribalism or indeed political party patronage, to reign supreme in civil service appointments, if failure must be avoided. This brings to mind the term used by President Muhammadu Buhari when he became President in 2015 that *“I belong to everybody and I belong to nobody”*..

Succinctly, the study reiterated that failure of public administrators in the quest for transformational change in the society is attributable to lack of leadership with profound knowledge, vision and courage. A successful transformation demands these elements. The personal journey to transformation can be both frightening and exhilarating. It demands energy and a deep commitment to learning and significant change. Change that reflects institutional development, by way of overcoming the confusions associated with coping with transformation and by adapting to the inherent complexity of the decision-making process through adoption of more agile and responsive governance processes.

In a nut shell, for public administrators to accomplish the desired transformation and avoid failure, the following should be taken into consideration: (i) public administrators should be able to identify strategies towards achieving societal goals and missions; (ii) public administrators should have the courage to provide visible and focused leadership; (iii) there should be effective communication amongst administrators, whether at the federal, state or local levels; (iv) there should be collaborative effort across functions and constituencies to achieve a constant and integrated set of support services for training and retraining of personnel, etc.

Recommendations

The study thus recommended as follows:

- Public administrator should endeavour to strive to achieve the highest standards in their work and to actively look for opportunities to improve on these standards.
- Public administrators should exhibit an act of loyalty to serve the duly elected Government of the day and should comply with the lawful instructions of their Ministers and senior managers to the best of their abilities.
- Public administrators should devote themselves wholly to the discharge of their work.
- Public administrators should not be seen to engage in political activities at places of work, nor allow their personal political views to influence the performance of their duties.
- Public servants should not seek or accept gifts, favours or inducements, financial or otherwise, in the course of discharging their duties. Nor will they offer gifts, favours or inducements.
- They should not use public properties or official time for their own private purposes.
- They should not use information acquired in the course of their official duties to gain personal financial advantage/reward.
- Public administrators should treat their clients and colleagues with courtesy. They should regard themselves as servants of the Nigerian people, and should be particularly considerate when dealing with vulnerable members of the public, such as the elderly, the poor, the sick and people with disabilities and other disadvantaged groups in the society.
- Public administrators are expected not to commit any unlawful act in the course of their duties, nor should they instruct or encourage any other person(s) to do so.
- Public servants/administrators should not be seen to unnecessarily withhold information which the public has a right to know or information which is needed by superior officers.

References

- Aghayere V. O. (2004) Eminent Administrative and Management Thinkers. In Administrative and Management Thought. H.S. Nnamdi, O.J. Offiong, D.A. Tonwe (eds). Amfitop Books. Pp.308-309. Amfitop Books.
- Akindele, S. T. (1995). Corruption: An Analytical Fuse on the Problems of its Conceptualization. *Ife PsycholoGIA* 3 (1), 84-85.
- Akinwale, A. A. (2010). Amnesty and human capital development agenda for Niger Delta. *Journal of African Studies and Development*, 2(8), 201-207.
- Arpomuvire, M. & Egbadju O. L. (2010). Security Contradiction: Bane of Reactions of Oil Producing Communities and the Ending Crisis in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. In V. Ogakoroku and L. Gilbert (eds). Checking the Resurgence of Oil Violence in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. [Http://www.icags.org/nigerdeltabrief](http://www.icags.org/nigerdeltabrief). Retrieved: February 20, 2011 and April 20, 2011.
- Cheema, G. S. (2004). From Public Administration To Governance: The Paradigm Shift In

The Link Between Government And Citizens. 6th Global Forum on Reinventing Government Towards Participatory and Transparent Governance 24 – 27 May 2005, Seoul, Republic of Korea.

- Deming, W. E. (1993), *The New Economics*, MIT Press, Cambridge.
- Drucker, P. (1994). The Age of Social Transformation. As originally published in *The Atlantic Monthly*, November 1994
- Gibson, K. & Cameron, J. (2001). “Transforming Communities: Towards A Research Agenda”. Published in *Urban Policy and Research Journal* 19, 1:7-24, 2001.
- Hazen, H. & Horner, J. (2007). *Small Arms, Armed Violence and Insecurity in Nigeria: The Niger Delta Perspective*. Switzerland: Co-print.
- Heifetz, R. A. & Linsky, M. (2002). “Leadership on the Line”, Harvard Business School Press, Boston.
- Kumolu, C. (2012). Nigeria's Problem is Poverty. <http://www.vanguarrdngr.com/2012/06>. accessed: April 20, 2011.
- Leon, P. B. (1979). Political Ideologies. Their Origin and Impact. Printed in the United States of America. 10 9 8 7. Prentice-Hall, Inc., Englewood Cliffs, N.J. 07632
- Makinde, T. (2005). Problems of Policy Implementation in Developing Nations: The Nigerian Experience. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 11(1): 63-69 (2005). p1.
- Manning, N. (2001) “The Legacy of the New Public Management in Developing Countries”, *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, Vol. 67: 297-312.
- Marwa, S.M. & Zairi, M/ (2009) “In Pursuit of Performance-oriented Civil Service Reforms (CSRs): A Kenyan Perspective”, *Measuring Business Excellence*, Vol. 13, No. 2: 34-43.
- Oaikhena, M. I. E. (2011). “Leadership Style: A Key to Rapid Growth and Development in Organization”. LIJOMASS. *Lapai International Journal of Management and Social Sciences*. Journal of the Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Ibrahim and Badamosi University Lapai, Niger State. Vol 4(2). Rock Printers. Pp.202-220.
- Ogunnowo, C.O & Oderinde, F.O. (2012) “Sustainable Development and Management of Infrastructure for Effective Transformation of Rural Communities In Nigeria: Implications For Food Security. *Ozean Journal of Social Sciences* 5(3), 2012. ISSN 1943-2577. Ozean Publication.
- Olaope, T. (2008). Theory and Practice of Public Administration and Civil Service Reforms in Nigeria. Spectrum books ltd. Nigeria. p9.
- Preboye, I.C. (2005). The Core Delta. Iduwini Clan. Otoukuku “The Lost Tribe”. Rural Development Nig. Ltd., Ibadan.
- Tzu, S. (2005). The Art of War. Shambhala pub. USA.
- Umoh, O., Thompson, A. & Adick, B. (2012). Effectiveness of Amnesty Programme in the Niger Delta: Differential Perception of Substance Using and Non Substance Using Ex-militants. A paper Presented at the 10th Biennial International Conference of CRISA, held at Rockview Hotel, Abuja, 10th - 12th July, 2012.
- Zimako, O.Z. (2009). Face of a Nation: Democracy in Nigeria, Foreign Relations and National Image. Nigeria in Semi Democratic Garb. Published by Modern Approach. India: Thomson Press.

